

Strategies for Improving the Study Habits of Post Primary School Students in Lagos State: Implication for Counselling

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Abstract

The study examined the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Nigeria. The scope of the study was limited to Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. Three research questions guided the study. This study employed the descriptive survey research design. Population of the Study consisted of all post primary school teachers and students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. Simple random sampling technique was utilized for selecting 10 post primary schools while purposive sampling method was employed in choosing the respondents. The instrument used for data collection was a research questionnaire titled: Strategies for Improving Post Primary School Students Study Habits Inventory (SIPPSSSHI). The researcher-made questionnaire was constructed in two sections, A and B. Section A involves the demographic information which include variables as gender, age, educational qualification while Section B was designed to measure the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students which was on a four point likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree). The instrument was given to Education experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, NOUN to ascertain its face and content validity and the corrected version was used in the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering it on a sample of 30 post primary school teachers and students in the Apapa local government area of Lagos State, which was not part of the original sample population. The data were analysed with the Cronbach alpha statistics. The coefficient of reliability obtained was 0.81 which was appropriate for the studies. The questionnaires were personally administered by the researchers to 200 respondents (100 teachers and 100 students) to ensure that copies of the questionnaire got to the respondents at the right time and subsequently retrieved. The data collected were analyzed with descriptive statistics and the Independent Sample Test (IST). The results of the study revealed that there are several strategies that can improve the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State; there is a significant difference between teachers and students views and between male and female respondents on the strategies to improve the study habits of Post primary school students. It was recommended among others that teachers should be adequately trained on the skills of guided reading to enable them device strategies to encourage students to study effectively and improve the academic performances of secondary schools students.

Key words: Strategies, Study habits, Post primary school, Students, Counselling

Introduction

Reading is the ability to understand words contained in a document and make use of the knowledge for personal growth and development (Dadzie, 2008). Reading is an essential tool for knowledge transfer and the habit of reading is an academic activity that increases skills in reading strategies. To know about the world and its environment, a child helps himself through reading books, newspapers and other magazines. Children, who miss the opportunity of getting in touch with books in their early stages of life, find it hard to acquire good reading habits in their later years (Deavers, 2000). Reading is an intellectual action which is possible only if a man forms a habit of reading and practices these from childhood. Reading habits, therefore, play a very crucial role in enabling students to achieve practical efficiency.

Reading habits are deliberate coordinated pattern of study by learners in order to enhance academic performance and excel in examinations. According to Palani (2012), reading habit is an essential and important aspect for creating a literate society in this world. According to him, effective reading is an important avenue of effective learning as reading is interrelated with the total educational process and hence, educational success requires successful reading habit. Good reading habits act as a strong weapon for the students to excel in life (Bashir&Mattoo, 2012). It shapes the personality of individuals and it helps them to develop proper thinking methods, and creates new ideas. Palani (2012) further added that, nowadays, reading habit has lost its importance as both the young and the old are glued to the television.

Study habits are defined as the devotion of time and attention to acquire information or knowledge especially from books. It is the pursuit of academic knowledge by a detailed investigation of a subject or situation (Oxford Dictionary & Thesaurus of English Language, 2003). It has long been recognized that in the process of learning, the study habits of the students play an important role in their academic performance (Palani, 2012). Both study habits and academic achievement are interrelated and dependent on each other. Good study habits act as a strong weapon for the students to excel in life. Good study habits lead to good academic record and bad study habits lead to poor academic record as there is direct relationship between study habits and academic achievement (Satapathy & Singhal, 2000; Vyas, 2002).

Many students fail not because they lack ability, but because they lack adequate study habit skills. It has been observed that hard working students with high IQs sometimes do not perform as well as their classmates with lower IQs (Harvey, 2011). Good students are not born but are made by constant and deliberate practice of good study habits, for which there is no substitute (Ames & Archer, 2008). The quality of a nation depends upon the quality of its citizens. The quality of citizens depends on the quality of their education and quality of education besides other factors depends upon study habits and study attitude of the learners. Quality of education is reflected through academic achievement which is a function of study habits and study attitude of the students. To enhance the quality of education, it is important to improve the study habits and study attitudes of the students.

Learners differ in the way they study. It is an exception that some students are able to breeze through school with minimal effort; the vast majority of successful students achieve their success by developing and applying effective study habits. According to Becton (2019), some

study habits strategies include: do not attempt to cram all your studying into one session, plan when you are going to study, study at the same time, each study time should have a specific goal, never procrastinate your planned study session, start with the most difficult subject first, always review your notes before starting an assignment, make sure you are not distracted while you are studying, use study groups effectively and review your notes, schoolwork and other class materials over the weekend.

The key to effective studying is not cramming or studying longer, but studying smarter (Grohol, 2019). You can begin studying smarter with these ten proven and effective study habits (Grohol, 2019). These habits include approaching study with the right attitude, choosing the right environment, minimizing distractions, setting a realistic schedule, and employing memory games, among others. Sylvan (2019) identified strategies like get organized, know the expectations, designate a study area, develop a study plan, think positively, create a study group, practice active listening, review test-taking strategies and look to the future, as good study habits that can help children to succeed in school.

Florida National University (FNU, 2019) highlighted nine helpful techniques to help prepare students on how they can improve their study habits. These techniques are: find a good studying spot, avoid social media, stay away from your phone, enlist the help of an app, take a break and take care of yourself, organize lectures notes, join or create a study group, plants and music and leave time for the last-minute review. Good study habits skills like note taking, having regular time to study, and organizing for a test, while removing the distraction that comes from television or phone call at home can lead to good academic performance (Tschumper, 2006). Effective study habits help students to achieve good results (Sadia, 2005).

Nuthanap (2007) observed that academic achievement of students at different levels of education appears to be deteriorating every year. The goal of helping students to acquire knowledge and the required skills may be hindered by poor study and irregular habits and ineffective practical lesson among secondary school students (Agidi, 2004). In Nigeria, there are many factors influencing the ability of students to cultivate effective and efficient study habit. Ozmert (2005) emphasized the importance of environmental influence as a major factor in the development of students study habits. For academic achievement, being smart is more important than being intelligent and hardworking and involves being practical, having common sense and using better organization and application of good study habits (Henk Schmidt, Loyens, Tamara & Fred, 2007).

Educational psychologists and researchers have argued that there are many determinants of academic performance (Chamorro-Permuzic & Furnham, 2003). Danskin and Burnett (2005) found that students getting higher marks had more effective study habits as compared to students who had ineffective study habits and thus lagged behind in studies. Thus, in order to improve academic performance of students, it seems essential to improve their study habits. Development of good study habits in students depends upon the combined efforts of parents and teachers (Kizlik, 2011). Singh (2011) examined academic achievement and study habits of higher secondary students. The study was conducted on hundred (100) higher secondary students randomly from two higher secondary schools. The result indicates that girls and boys differ significantly in their

study habits and academic achievement. Bhan and Gupta (2010) on the other hand examined study habits and academic achievement among the students belonging to scheduled caste and non-scheduled caste group. The results revealed that sex has no significant impact on the study habits and academic achievement of students. Dadzie (2008) found that girls and boys differ significantly in their study habits and academic achievement. Sharma (2004) assessed the study habits and underachievement among rural girls. The results revealed significant differences in the study habits scores of under and high achievers.

Briggs (2001) researched on the study habits modification and its effect on academic performance. The results revealed that study habits have a good effect on the academic performance of “high-risk” students. Similarly, Crow and Crow (1963) in Bashir and Mattoo (2012) found academically poor achievers to have less effective study habits as compared to academically high achievers. In the same context, Bashir and Mattoo (2012) found that pupils who got more scholarships had better study habits than the pupils who did not achieve scholarships. Despite possessing good intelligence and personality, the absence of good study habits hampers academic achievement. Perhaps, due to lack of good reading habits among students, academic performance with respect to their examination result has been dismal nowadays creating a great source of worry and concern for all stakeholders in the educational sub-sector (Issa et al, 2012). The fact that some students with apparently high scholastic aptitude do very poorly in high school while others with only mediocre ability do very well has presented a challenge to many educators. There seems to be no clear and simple answer to this complex but very important observation. The study therefore sought to determine the strategies for improving the study habits of the post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Statement of the Problem

The academic achievement of students at different levels of education appears to be deteriorating every year. The goal of helping students to attain their desired careers in life and the acquired the needed skills may be a mirage due to poor study habits.

Consequently, it has been realized that students who possess adequate mental abilities sometimes do not perform well in their academic work either because they do not know how to study effectively or they do not use the most effective strategies of studying. Non application of appropriate study habit strategies by post primary school students have resulted in poor grades, not attaining their inherent potentials and excel in their life carriers. An attempt to help students achieve their educational goals and career ambitions and mitigate the declining academic performances prompted the researchers to investigate the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Objectives of the Study

The study examined the Strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

2. The difference between teachers' and students' views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.
3. The difference between male and female respondents' views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State?

Research Questions

1. What are the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State?
2. Is there any difference between teachers' and students' view on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State?
3. Is there any difference between male and female respondents' views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State?

Method

This study employed the descriptive survey research design whose purpose was to collect detailed and factual information that describes an existing phenomenon. The descriptive survey research design was seen to be the most desirable because it enables the researcher to measure the variables under consideration. Population of the study consisted of all teachers and students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. Simple random technique was utilized in selecting 10 post primary schools while purposive sampling method was employed in choosing the respondents for the study.

The instrument used for data collection for this study was a research questionnaire titled: Strategies for Improving Post Primary School Students Inventory (SIPPSSHI). The researcher-made questionnaire was constructed in two sections, A and B. Section A involves the demographic information which include variables as gender, social status and educational qualifications while Section B was designed with questions to measure the strategies to improve post primary school students. Respondents were asked to report their level of agreement on a four point likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 4 (Strongly agree). The instrument was given to Education experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, NOUN to ascertain its face and content validity and the corrected version was used in the study. The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering it on a sample of 30 Post Primary school teachers and students in Apalocal government area of Lagos State, which was not part of the original sample population. The data obtained were analysed with the Cronbach alpha statistics. The coefficient of reliability was 0.81 which was appropriate for the studies

The questionnaires were personally administered by the researchers to ensure that copies of the questionnaire got to the respondents at the right time and subsequently retrieved. 200 respondents (100 teachers and 100 students) were administered with the instrument and those retrieved were 180, thereby constituting about 90%. The data from the questionnaires administered was collected from the respondents and analysed using statistical packages for

social sciences (SPSS) Descriptive statistics, mean rating and t-test to determine the independent and the dependent variables. All the research questions were examined at 0.05 alpha levels of significance. The average weighted mean of 2.5 was used to evaluate the statistics.

Results

Research questions 1: What are the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos?

Table: 1.

Mean rating on the strategies for improving the study habits of Post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

S/N	Statement	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q1	Employing memory games can help to improve study habit	180	505.08	2.81	.42	Agreed
Q2	Setting a realistic schedule can help to improve study habit	180	348.04	3.03	.27	Agreed
Q3	Create a study group can help to improve study habit	180	538.28	2.96	.23	Agreed
Q4	Approaching study with the right attitude can help to improve study habit	180	559.08	3.10	.34	Agreed
Q5	Review test-taking strategies can help to improve study habit	180	543.06	3.02	.41	Agreed
Q6	Efficient management of time improves study habit	180	554.04	3.08	.39	Agreed
Q7	Organize lectures notes improves study habit	180	538.02	2.99	.55	Agreed
Q8	Start with the most difficult subject first can help to improve study habit	180	540.00	3.00	.35	Agreed
Q9	Removing the distraction that comes from social media	180	563.04	3.13	.41	Agreed
Q10	Designate a good studying environment can help to improve study habit	180	576.00	3.20	.42	Agreed
	Total	1800	5264.64	3.03	.38	Agreed

Table 1 revealed the mean rating on the strategies for improving post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. Designate a good studying environment can help to improve study habit top the list with average mean score of 3.20, closely followed by removing the distraction that comes from social media (3.13); again by approaching study with the right attitude (3.10); Setting a realistic schedule (3.03). The total average mean was 3.03, which was above the average mean of 2.5. The implication is that there are several strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State

Research question 2: Is there any difference between teachers and students views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State?

Table: 2.

T-test analysis on the difference between teachers and students views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t	Sig.
Teachers	96	2.02	.00	.00	178	57.21	.000
Students	84	1.05	.194	.02			

0.05 levels of significance

The result in Table 2 shows that there is significant difference between teachers and students views on the strategies for improving the study habits of Post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State, at $t(57.21) = df,178, P<.05$. Research question2, which states that thereis no significant difference between teachers’ and students’ views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos state, was rejected. The implication is that there is a significant difference of 0.97 between teachers’ and students’ views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Research questions 3: Is there any difference between male and female respondents’ views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State?

Table 3:

T-test analysis on the difference between male and female respondents’ views on the strategies for improving the study habits of Post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	T	Sig.
Male	78	3.56	.00	.00	178	40.24	.000
Female	102	2.74	.194	.02			

0.05 levels of significance

The result in Table 3revealeda significant difference between male and female respondents’ view on the strategies for improving post primary school students, at $t(40.24), df=178, P<.05$. Research question 3, which states that there is no significant difference between male and female respondents’ views on the strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State, was rejected. The implication is that

there is a significant difference of 0, 82 between male and female respondents' views on the Strategies for improving the study habits of Post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveal that there are several strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. The outcome correlates with the assertion of Bashir and Mattoo (2012) that good reading habits act as a strong weapon for the students to excel in life. Educational psychologists and researchers have argued that there are many determinants of academic performance (Chamorro-Permuzic & Furnham, 2003). Danskin and Burnett (2005) found that students getting higher marks had more effective study habits as compared to students who had ineffective study habits and thus lagged behind in studies. Good study habits like note taking, having regular time to study, and organizing for a test, while removing the distraction that comes from television or phone call at home can lead to good academic performance (Tschumper, 2006). Effective study habits help students to achieve good results (Sadia, 2005). According to Becton (2019), some study habits strategies include: do not attempt to cram all your studying into one session, plan when you are going to study, study at the same time, each study time should have a specific goal, never procrastinate your planned study session, start with the most difficult subject first, always review your notes before starting an assignment, make sure you're not distracted while you are studying, use study groups effectively and review your notes, schoolwork and other class materials over the weekend.

Sylvan (2019) identified strategies like get organized, know the expectations, designate a study area, develop a study plan, think positively, create a study group, practice active listening, review test-taking strategies, review test-taking strategies and look to the future, as good study habits that can help children to succeed in school. Ozmert (2005) emphasized the importance of environmental influence as a major factor in the development of students study habits.

The finding of this study also reveals that there is a significant difference between teachers and students views on the strategies to improve the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. This outcome correlates with the finding of Charles-Ogan and Alamina (2014) that learning is a matter of personal habits.

Another finding of this study revealed that there is a significant difference between male and female respondents' views on the strategies to improve the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State. This finding is in consonant with Singh (2011) who indicated that girls and boys differ significantly in their study habits and academic achievement. Dadzie (2008) found that girls and boys differ significantly in their study habits and academic achievement. Also, Sharma (2004) assessed the study habits and underachievement among rural girls. The results revealed significant differences in the study habits scores of under and high achievers. The finding runs contrary to Bhan and Gupta (2010) who examined study habits and academic achievement among the students belonging to scheduled caste and non-

scheduled caste group. The results revealed that sex has no significant impact on the study habits and academic achievement of students.

Implication for counseling

The major goal of school counselors is to help students actualize their academic potentials and attain maximum growth in their chosen careers. Counsellors should therefore use the findings of this study to inculcate the strategies to develop good study habits in students. This is necessary because there is no academic success without the acquisitions of knowledge through good study habits. This could be done through orientation programmes, seminars and workshops.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study and the discussion that followed, the study concludes that there are several strategies for improving the study habits of post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State, there is a significant difference between teachers' and students' views and between male and female respondents' views on the Strategies for improving the study habits of Post primary school students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on research findings:

1. Teachers should be adequately trained on the skills of guided reading to enable them devise strategies to encourage students to study effectively and improve the academic performances of secondary schools students in Eti-osa Local Government Area of Lagos State.
2. School administrators should provide the enabling environment for secondary schools students to improve their study habits in order to excel in their chosen profession.
3. Government should build public libraries in every major city to encourage reading culture among students.

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